

A rhodamine-based fluorescent sensor for rapid detection of Hg^{2+} exhibiting aggregation induced enhancement of emission (AIEE) in aqueous surfactant medium

Dipankar Das^a, Rahul Bhowmick^a, Atul Katarkar^b, Keya Chaudhuri^b and Mahammad Ali^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Jadavpur, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : m_ali2062@yahoo.com Fax : 91-33-24146223

^bDepartment of Molecular & Human Genetics Division, CSIR-Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, 4, Raja S. C. Mallick Road, Kolkata-700 032, India

Manuscript received 20 June 2017, accepted 25 June 2017

Abstract : An easily synthesizable rhodamine-based chemosensor, L_2 , selectively recognizes Hg^{2+} and Al^{3+} ions in the presence of all biologically relevant and toxic heavy metal ions. Very low detection limit (47 nM for Hg^{2+}) along with cell permeability and negligible cytotoxicity provides a good opportunity towards cell imaging of Hg^{2+} . SEM studies reveal rod-like microstructure for L_2 in water, which changes to a porous microstructure in the presence of Hg^{2+} . It was interesting to note that the presence of SDS solubilized the otherwise insoluble probe in pure aqueous medium. In case of Al^{3+} it was astonishingly observed a fluorescence quenching on increasing the SDS concentration, while a ~ 33 -fold enhancement of FI of $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complex was observed compared to that in the absence of SDS, making the probe selective towards Hg^{2+} over Al^{3+} in the aqueous SDS medium. In SDS/water system, there is a steep rise in FI, reaches a maximum at ~ 7 mM of SDS and then fluorescence intensity decreases gradually with the increase in [SDS] up to 28 mM. These observations clearly signify the SDS-assisted formation of polymer aggregates of the complex on the surface of monolayer of SDS formed in pre-micellar concentrations with higher FI, which is converted to the monomer being trapped inside the micellar cavity beyond the critical micellar concentration (cmc) with comparatively lower FI, indicating an interesting AIEE phenomenon. This proposition is further supported by the dependence of fluorescence anisotropy (r) on [SDS].

Keywords : Rhodamine-based turn-on Hg^{2+} sensor, aggregation induced enhancement of emission (AIEE), fluorescence anisotropy (r), microstructure formation, live cell imaging.

Introduction

The fabrication of appealing supramolecular assemblies are achieved through bottom-up approach by an elegant use of noncovalent interactions like electrostatic, hydrophobic, van der Waals, hydrogen bonding etc.¹⁻⁴. Out of these, ionic self-assembly by various combinations between peptides, polyelectrolytes, surfactants and extended rigid organic scaffolds has attracted considerable attention of the researchers due to its application towards the fabrication of optical materials and advanced nano-devices. Another interesting feature of these supramolecular assemblies is their different behaviour in solution and solid state exhibit-

ing either aggregation induced emission enhancement (AIEE) or aggregation caused quenching (ACQ)⁵⁻⁹. Till date, the AIEE mechanism has been observed in silole derivative¹⁰, 1,1,2,2-tetraphenylethene (TPE)¹¹⁻¹³, 1-cyano-*trans*-1,2-bis-(4-methylphenyl)ethylene (CN-MBE) etc.^{14,15}.

The amphiphilic nature of surfactants readily produces various supramolecular aggregates like micelles and vesicles in aqueous solution^{16,17}. It could be used as a coupling unit to induce structural changes by ionic self-assembly. Recently surfactants have been suitably exploited to generate AIEE¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Heavy metals like mercury, lead, cadmium and

semimetal arsenic²¹ are widely distributed, extensively used, and highly toxic, and pose the greatest environmental threat; as soils and sediments are the ultimate sink for them. The water-soluble Hg²⁺ ion is highly toxic and can damage the brain, nervous system, kidneys, and endocrine system^{22,23}. Again, due to very high thiophilicity Hg²⁺ can deactivate many thiol-containing enzymes, thereby stopping or altering the metabolic processes²⁴⁻²⁶. Over the past decade, increasing attention has been paid to the development of efficient chromo- and fluorogenic sensors for Hg²⁺ ions for real-time monitoring of environmental, biological and industrial samples²⁷⁻³⁵.

Here, a rhodamine-based probe with potential NO₃ donor atoms have been synthesized and used successfully for the selective and rapid recognition of toxic Hg²⁺ ion (Scheme 1) exhibiting chromo- and fluorogenic metal-induced OFF-ON responses through the opening of the spirolactam ring.

In addition, although the current probe is poorly soluble in 100% aqueous medium, the presence of SDS makes it soluble in this medium, thereby making it useful for monitoring Hg²⁺ ion in the purely aqueous

medium in the presence of SDS with enhanced sensitivity and selectivity, even in the presence of Al³⁺ which otherwise gives fluorescence response with the probe in the absence of SDS^{19,20}.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

All solvents used for the synthetic purposes were of reagent grade (Merck). For spectroscopic (UV/Vis and fluorescence) studies double-distilled water and HPLC-grade MeCN were used. Rhodamine 6G hydrochloride, ethylene diamine, methyl acrylate and perchlorate salts of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Cu²⁺ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. Sodium salts of anions like SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, S²⁻, Cl⁻, F⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, OAc⁻, H₂AsO₄⁻ and N₃⁻ were of reagent grade and used as received.

Steady-state fluorescence studies were carried out with a PTI (QM-40) spectrofluorimeter. UV/Vis absorption spectra were recorded with an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer. Bruker spectrometers of 300 and 500 MHz were used for ¹H and ¹³C NMR

Scheme 1. Synthetic steps leading the formation of [L₂-Hg²⁺] complex.

Das *et al.* : A rhodamine-based fluorescent sensor for rapid detection of Hg²⁺ exhibiting aggregation *etc.*

studies. The ESI-MS⁺ spectra were recorded on a Waters XEVO G2QTof (Micro YA263) mass spectrometer.

Synthesis of rhodamine 6G hydrazide (L₁) :

It was synthesized by the literature method³⁶.

Synthesis of rhodamine 6G probe (L₂) :

To a suspension of 30 mL ice-cooled (0 °C) methanolic solution of L₁ (0.456 g, 1.0 mM), a 4 mL methanol solution of methylacrylate (0.36 mL, 10 mmol) was added dropwise over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm slowly to room temperature at which it was stirred for 3 days. The final product was obtained after evaporation of methylacrylate and methanol under vacuum as white crystals (yield 0.55 g, 88%) with m.p. 134–136 °C, *R_f* = 0.66 in a toluene/ethanol = 2 : 1 solvent system.

FT-IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3324 (-NH); 2942, 2896 (-CH); 1723 (-C=O); 1670 (-COOMe); 1622, 1518 and 1450 (-ArCH).

¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz), δ ppm : 7.75–7.77 (1H, t, -Ar-H), 7.48–7.53 (2H, m, Ph-H), 6.98–7.00 (1H, t, -Ar-H), 6.25 (2H, s, Ph-H), 6.03 (2H, s, -Ar-H), 5.0 (2H, t, ArNHCH₂), 3.33 (6H, s, -COOCH₃), 3.09–3.17 (4H, m, ArNHCH₂), 2.89–2.92 (2H, t, -CH₂NCOAr), 2.42–2.44 (4H, t, -CH₂-CH₂COOMe), 2.11–2.14 (4H, t, -CH₂-COOMe), 2.01–2.05 (2H, t, -CH₂-N), 1.88 (6H, s, -ArCH₃), 1.18–1.20 (6H, t, -CH₂CH₃); ES⁺ MS = 629.3890 [L₂+H⁺].

Methods of characterization :

A scanning electron microscope (SEM) (ZEOL, JSM 8360) operating at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV was used for the study of morphologies of the free probe (L₂) in aqueous medium and also in the presence of Hg²⁺ (L₂-Hg²⁺). Before SEM, the samples were vacuum dried and then gold coated to minimize the sample charging.

Fluorescence anisotropies (*r*), defined by eq. (1), were measured on a PTI QM-40 spectrofluorometer.

$$r = (I_{VV} - G \cdot I_{VH}) / (I_{VV} + 2G \cdot I_{VH}) \quad (1)$$

where, *I_{VV}* and *I_{VH}* indicate the emission intensities

with the excitation polarizer oriented vertically and emission polarizer oriented vertically and horizontally, respectively, and corresponding *G* factor is calculated as in eq. (2)¹⁹;

$$G = I_{HV} / I_{HH} \quad (2)$$

where, *I_{HV}* and *I_{HH}* refer to the intensities corresponding to the vertical and horizontal positions of the emission polarizer, with the excitation polarizer being horizontal.

Cell culture and cell cytotoxicity assay :

HepG2 (Human hepatocellular liver carcinoma) cell lines (NCCS, Pune, India) grown in DMEM was supplemented with 10% FBS and antibiotics (penicillin – 100 µg/ml; streptomycin – 50 µg/ml). Conditions for the culture of cells are : 37 °C in 95% air, 5% CO₂ incubator. To test the cytotoxicity of L₂, the 3-(4,5-di-methylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay was performed following the procedure described previously^{36–39}.

Cell imaging studies :

Cell imaging studies were performed by using the protocol as described previously^{36–39}.

Results and discussion

A simple reaction between L₁ and methyl acrylate in methanol leads to the formation of L₂ in quantitative yield (Scheme 1) which was thoroughly characterized by ¹H NMR (Fig. S1), ¹³C NMR (Fig. S2), ESI-MS⁺ (Fig. S3) and IR studies (Fig. S4a).

Steady-state absorption and emission studies :

The UV-Vis titrations reveals that on gradual addition of Hg²⁺ to a 50 µM solution of L₂ there occurs a gradual growing of two peaks at 350 nm and 528 nm (Fig. S5) clearly manifesting the chelation induced opening of the spirolactam ring of the probe. The probable coordination mode of L₂ towards Hg²⁺ is demonstrated in Scheme 1. When absorbances were plotted against [Hg²⁺] it gives a non-linear curve of decreasing slope (Fig. S5). Eq. (3)¹⁹ was employed to solve such dependence with *a* and *b* as the absorbance in the absence and presence of excess metal ions, *c* (= *K_f*) is the apparent formation constant and *n* is the stoichio-

Fig. 1. Fluorescence titration of L_2 (20 μM) in MeCN- H_2O (1 : 1, v/v) in HEPES buffer at pH 7.2 by the gradual addition of Hg^{2+} (0–130 μM) with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502$ nm. Inset : linear curve-fit of FI vs $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ plot.

Fig. 2. Fluorescence titration of L_2 (20 μM) in MeCN- H_2O (1 : 1, v/v) in HEPES buffer at pH 7.2 by the gradual addition of Al^{3+} (0–130 μM) with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502$ nm. Inset : linear curve-fit of FI vs $[\text{Al}^{3+}]$ plot.

metry of the reaction. The evaluated apparent association constant K_f is $(3.08 \pm 0.53) \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ with $n = 1.0$.

$$y = \frac{a + bx^n}{1 + cx^n} \quad (3)$$

Job's method also gives 1 : 1 (Fig. S6) complexation between L_2 and Hg^{2+} which was further supported by mass spectrometric analysis ($m/z = 440.2579$)

$[\text{Hg}(L_2)(\text{MeOH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ (see Fig. S3a in the Supporting Information).

The fluorescence titration was carried out by gradual addition of Hg^{2+} (0–130 μM) to a fixed concentration of L_2 (20 μM) in MeCN/water (1 : 1, v/v, HEPES buffer, pH 7.2) which yielded ~ 126 -fold enhancement in fluorescence intensity at 558 nm on excitation at 502 nm (Fig. 1). The titration data were again solved by employing eq. (3) under the condition $1 \gg c \times x^n$ with $n = 1$ prevailing a linear form. A linear least-square fitting of data gives the apparent association constant $K_f = (1.01 \pm 0.01) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (see Fig. 1 inset). Al^{3+} also induces an opening of spirolactam ring of the probe leading to enhancement of fluorescence intensity. So, analogously the fluorescence titration data for L_2 - Al^{3+} complexation was solved and the apparent formation constant was calculated to be $(1.45 \pm 0.02) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2 inset)

Selectivity of the probe :

The probe was found to be sensitive towards Hg^{2+} , but interfered by the presence of Al^{3+} . However, in the presence of SDS in aqueous medium the fluorescence of L_2 - Al^{3+} was completely quenched, but not the L_2 - Hg^{2+} complex, instead there was an increase in FI (*vide infra*). In case of L_2 - Al^{3+} complexation the quenching of fluorescence intensity may arise due to abstraction of Al^{3+} from the $[\text{L}_2\text{-Al}^{3+}]$ complex by SDS arising out of strong hard-hard interaction between sulfonic-O and Al^{3+} ion; which is absent for L_2 - Hg^{2+} complex. Again, the detection of Hg^{2+} was not perturbed by 5 equivalents of metal ions like Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} (Fig. 3) under the identical reaction conditions. Also, the introduction of 5 equivalents of anions like SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , S^{2-} , CN^- , Cl^- , F^- , Br^- , I^- , OAc^- , H_2AsO_4^- and N_3^- into the solution of L_2 (Fig. S7) did not show any appreciable fluorescence change. However, I^- has a strong affinity towards Hg^{2+} . As a result I^- abstracts Hg^{2+} ion from the $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complex resulting the disappearance of emission band at 558 nm through the re-establishment of the spirolactam ring (Fig. S8). The quantum yield (ϕ) of the $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complex and ligand were determined to be 0.8609 and

0.011 respectively (rhodamine 6G as a standard). The limits of detection (LOD) of Hg^{2+} and Al^{3+} were found to be as low as 47 and 73 nM, respectively (Fig. S9) as delineated by 3σ method. The increased quantum yield (ϕ) and lifetime (τ) of $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ over the free ligand L_2 clearly indicate the enhanced stability of the formed complex in the excited state.

pH-stability of the probe was checked over a wide range of pH (2–12). There is no obvious fluorescence emission of L_2 in the range of pH 4–12, establishing the fact that the spirolactam form of L_2 is stable over this wide pH range (Fig. S10). However, the presence Hg^{2+} ion induces the opening of spirolactam ring at $\text{pH} \geq 7.0$ resulting a fluorescence enhancement and hence seems to be compatible for biological applications under physiological conditions.

IR studies showed a characteristic amidic “C=O” stretching frequency of the rhodamine moiety at 1723 cm^{-1} which is shifted to a lower wave number (1657 cm^{-1}) in the presence of 1.2 equivalent of Hg^{2+} (Fig. S4b). Thus a strong binding of L_2 to the Hg^{2+} ion and the cleavage of N-C bond in spirolactam ring is apparent. The ^1H NMR spectra showed the ring proton “b” (Fig. 4 and Fig. S1) of the rhodamine moiety is shifted downfield in the presence of 1.2 equivalents of Hg^{2+} ions. The “f” proton of $-\text{NH}^+$ group vanishes as

Fig. 3. (a) Histogram of the fluorescence responses of different metal ions (100 mM) towards L_2 (20 mM) in 1 : 1 v/v MeCN/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.2 with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502\text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 558\text{ nm}$. (b) Fluorescence responses of different cations (100 mM) towards L_2 (20 mM) in 1 : 1 v/v MeCN/water in HEPES buffer at pH 7.2.

Fig. 4. ^1H NMR spectra of (a) L_2 and (b) L_2 in presence of 1.2 equivalent of Hg^{2+} . Both spectra were recorded on a Bruker 500 MHz spectrometer in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ (For atom numbering, please see Fig. S1).

this group possesses a positive charge due to ring opening upon binding with Hg^{2+} ion. The “a” proton also shows a down-field shift. The down-field shift of “a” and “b” protons in the presence of Hg^{2+} arises mainly due to decrease in electron density on opening of the spirolactam ring. The signal pattern of the other aromatic protons in $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ also indicates the involvement of the receptor unit of L_2 in the binding to Hg^{2+} .

Time resolved fluorescence studies :

The fluorescence decay behaviour of the L_2 and $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ were studied in aqueous medium (Fig. S11) both in the absence and presence of SDS. The bi-exponential decay of L_2 resulted life times of 1.53 ns (τ_1) and 6.11 ns (τ_2). But in the presence of SDS it prevails a mono-exponential decay with $\tau = 3.63\text{ ns}$. In the presence of Hg^{2+} the decay processes are mono-exponential both in the absence and presence of SDS with respective τ values of 4.47 and 5.44 ns (Fig. S11). Bi-exponential decay of free ligand may arise due to $\pi\cdots\pi$ stacking interactions between the probe molecules. The enhanced life time of L_2 and $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complex in the presence of SDS may arise due to enhanced stability of the probe and its complex in the

Fig. 5. (a) Fluorescence titration of L_2 ($20 \mu\text{M}$) by Hg^{2+} ($0\text{--}40 \mu\text{M}$) in presence of $[\text{SDS}] = 7 \text{ mM}$ with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502 \text{ nm}$. (b) Plot of fluorescence intensity as a function of $[\text{SDS}]$.

excited state in the presence of SDS. Thus this observation clearly indicates the fact that SDS imposes more restriction on the movement of the probe in micro-heterogeneous environments through the formation polymeric aggregates.

Steady-state fluorescence studies in aqueous SDS :

In purely aqueous solution the $L_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}$ complex is weakly fluorescent, however, in the presence of SDS enhanced fluorescence was observed. Thus, steady state fluorescence studies were also carried out in the presence of SDS in two separate experiments. In one case, the SDS concentration was kept fixed at 7 mM and $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ was varied in the range $0\text{--}40 \mu\text{M}$ giving a non-linear curve of decreasing slope which was solved by adopting eq. (3) (Fig. 5b) and evaluated apparent formation constant $K_f = (1.00 \pm 0.02) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ was found to be an order of magnitude higher than that obtained in the absence of SDS. This enhanced stability constant value may be due to the restricted movement of the doubly positively charged $L_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}$ complex, which were held fixed in position by the strong electrostatic interaction with the negatively charged sulphonic acid head groups of SDS in the form of layer structure. This causes the formation of aggregates of $L_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}$ complex through strong cooperative

Scheme 2. Schematic presentation of the formation of polymeric aggregates and monomer in presence of SDS before and after the cmc. Adopted from <http://www.ecoboss.com.au/img/micelle.jpg>.

$\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions among the complexes held sidewise (Scheme 2).

In another experiment both $[L_2]$ and $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ was kept fixed at 20 and $150 \mu\text{M}$, respectively and $[\text{SDS}]$ was varied between $0\text{--}28 \text{ mM}$. A plot of FI vs $[\text{SDS}]$ showed a gradual increase in FI with the increase in $[\text{SDS}]$, reaches a maximum at $\sim 7 \text{ mM}$ and then gradually decreases with the increase in $[\text{SDS}]$ (Fig. 6b). The fluorescence maximum at $[\text{SDS}] \sim 7 \text{ mM}$ clearly points out a critical micellar concentration (CMC) of SDS as $\sim 7 \text{ mM}$ under the experimental conditions. The decrease in FI with $[\text{SDS}]$ beyond 7 mM may be attributed to a change in polymeric aggregates of the complex to a monomer arising due to the formation of spherical micelle on increasing the $[\text{SDS}]$ (Scheme 2) in which the complex is trapped. The increase in FI with $[\text{SDS}]$ manifests the fact of aggregation induced enhancement (AIE) of fluorescence. In the case of Al^{3+} ion, fluorescence quenching was observed on increasing the concentration of SDS (Fig. 6c) and may be explained by considering the fact that sulphonic acid group abstract Al^{3+} ion from $[L_2\text{-Al}^{3+}]$ complex by strong electrostatic interaction. So in aqueous SDS the probe becomes more selective towards Hg^{2+} . The fluorescence quenching experiment by iodide ion in the presence of $[\text{SDS}] = 7 \text{ mM}$ was carried out to verify such a proposition and was evaluated to be $K_{\text{SV}} = (7.23 \pm 4.3) \times 10^6$ indicating an easy accessibility of the $[L_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complex located on the lamellar surface of the SDS to I^- ion to form HgI_2 .

Fig. 6. (a) Fluorescence titration of L_2 (20 μM) by [SDS] in presence of $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ (130 μM) with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502$ nm; (b) plot of fluorescence intensity as a function of [SDS]; (c) fluorescence titration of L_2 (20 μM) by [SDS] in presence of $[\text{Al}^{3+}]$ (130 μM) with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502$ nm; (d) plot of fluorescence intensity as a function of [SDS].

Determination of steady-state fluorescence anisotropy :

Steady-state fluorescence anisotropy is usually taken as a measure of the extent of restriction imposed by the micro heterogeneous environments on the dynamic properties of the probe. An increase in rigidity of the fluorophore results in an increase in the fluorescence anisotropy¹⁹. We have monitored the fluorescence anisotropy as a function of SDS concentration at a fixed concentration of L_2 and Hg^{2+} (20 and 150 μM , respectively) at 558 nm which showed a marked increase in anisotropy on increasing SDS concentration up to 3.5 mM, then gradually decreases with SDS concentration reaches a plateau at ~ 5 mM and maintains steady value up to 12 mM. In the range 1–3.5 mM concentration, the SDS arranges them in a layered fashion. Now, the doubly charged $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complexes are held firmly by the strong electrostatic interactions between negatively charged sulfonic acid head groups and doubly positively charged complexes; which are again held together by strong $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions thereby restricting their free movement. As a result, there occurs a sharp increase in anisotropy in the [SDS] ~ 1 –3.5 mM. Further increase in the SDS concentration, a phase transition occurs through the formation of micelle. The slight drop in r values with [SDS] beyond 3.5 mM may be rationalized by considering the formation of a monomer of $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complex

which is again trapped inside the cavity of the micelle. The higher values of r in case of polymeric aggregates arise due to cooperative interactions among the $[\text{L}_2\text{-Hg}^{2+}]$ complexes which is absent in monomer trapped inside the cavity of the micelle. The variation of fluorescence anisotropy (r) as a function of SDS concentration is presented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Plot of fluorescence anisotropy (r) as a function of [SDS] in purely aqueous medium at 25 °C and $[\text{L}_2] = [\text{Hg}^{2+}] = 20$ μM , $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 502$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 558$ nm.

SEM study :

The SEM micrographs of L_2 (0.50 mM) prevails rod-like microstructures which interestingly changes to porous like architecture in presence of Hg^{2+} (0.50 mM) (Fig. 8). In case of pure ligand in water the

Fig. 8. SEM images of microstructures conditions : (i) L_2 0.5 mM and (ii) $L_2 + Hg^{2+}$ (0.5 mM each) in aqueous medium.

structures are similar to the hexagonal prisms that arises due to the presence of two different polar ends (xanthine moiety and carboxylic ester moiety) favoring the stacking of L_2 one over another. However, in presence of Hg^{2+} these stacking interactions are disrupted leading to the formation of porous microstructures centering Hg^{2+} with the ligands at the periphery.

Cell imaging applications :

Hg^{2+} capturing capability of L_2 was assessed by performing the fluorescence imaging of L_2 with Hg^{2+} into the live HepG2 cells (Fig. 9). The cytotoxicity effects of L_2 determined by MMT assay indicate no significant cell cytotoxicity for HepG2 cells up to 60 μM (<30% cytotoxicity) of L_2 (Fig. S13). Interestingly, up to 10 μM of L_2 there was more than 90% of cell viability and fluorescence imaging were carried out at 1 μM , 5 μM and 10 μM of L_2 . Significantly, an excellent red intracellular cytoplasmic fluorescence was observed inside the live HepG2 cells pre-incubated with 10 μM of Hg^{2+} followed by washing with 1X PBS and subsequent incubation with 1 μM , 5 μM and 10 μM of L_2 . Interestingly, we observed that L_2 has excellent Hg^{2+} capturing capability even at low concentration likely at 1 μM and 5 μM at cytoplasmic level of Hg^{2+} ions (Fig. 9). Moreover, the concentration dependent binding of the L_2 with Hg^{2+} ions was observed (Fig. 9). Parallel staining of cells were carried out with DAPI and superimposed with the correspondingly treated cells with Hg^{2+} (10 μM) followed by L_2 (10, 1, 5, 10 μM) to show the cytoplasmic staining of L_2 with HepG2 cells.

Fig. 9. Cell imaging study of Hg^{2+} ions with L_2 . The fluorescence images of HepG2 cells were captured (40X and 100X) after incubated with 10 μM of L_2 for 30 min at 37 $^{\circ}C$, also in pre-incubated 10 μM of Hg^{2+} for 3 h at 37 $^{\circ}C$ followed by washing twice with 1X PBS and, subsequent incubation with 1 μM , 5 μM and 10 μM of ligand L_2 for 30 min at 37 $^{\circ}C$. The imaging studies showed the strong red fluorescence when L_2 binds with cytoplasmic Hg^{2+} ions. The merge images show the cytoplasmic Hg^{2+} - L_2 fluorescence.

Conclusions

In summary, we present herein a rhodamine-based chemosensor with potential NO₃ donor atoms for the selective and rapid recognition of toxic Hg²⁺ ions. The binding stoichiometry of the sensor with Hg²⁺ was established by the combined Job's and HRMS (*m/z*) methods. All biologically relevant as well as toxic heavy metal ions did not interfere with the detection of Hg²⁺ ion. The detection limit of Hg²⁺ calculated by 3σ method gives a value of 1.52 nM. Its exhibits live cell imaging application of Hg²⁺ with no or negligible cytotoxicity. SEM studies reveal a rod-like microstructure for L₂ which changes to a porous microstructure in presence of Hg²⁺ (0.50 mM). The presence of SDS causes enhanced quantum yield (θ), life time (τ), and stability constant (K_p) by an order of magnitude compared to those in the absence of SDS. Again, the FI of [L₂-Hg²⁺] complex is enhanced by 33-fold in the presence of 7 mM SDS to that in the absence of SDS. In SDS/water system, there is a steep rise in FI with the increase in [SDS], reaches a maximum at ~7 mM and then FI decreases gradually with the increase in [SDS] up to 28 mM, indicating the formation of polymeric aggregates of [L₂-Hg²⁺] complex on layers of the SDS at pre-micellar concentrations with higher FI values – a phenomenon reminiscent with the aggregation induced emission enhancement (AIEE). However, it turns into monomer and trapped inside the cavity of the micelle beyond CMC with comparatively lower FI. This proposition is further supported by the dependence of fluorescence anisotropy (*r*) with [SDS].

Acknowledgement

Financial supports from DST, New Delhi (Ref. SR/S1/IC-20/2012) and UGC CAS-II are gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. F. J. M. Hoeben, P. L. Jonkheijm, E. W. Meijer and A. P. H. J. Schenning, *Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **105**, 1491.
2. T. L. Greaves and C. J. Drummond, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2008, **37**, 1709.
3. T. H. Rehm and C. Schmuck, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 3597.
4. T. L. Greaves and C. J. Drummond, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2013, **42**, 1096.
5. B. K. An, J. Gierschner and S. Y. Park, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2012, **45**, 544.
6. X. Luo, J. Li, C. Li, L. Heng, Y. Q. Dong, Z. Liu, Z. Bo and B. Z. Tang, *Adv. Mater.*, 2011, **23**, 3261.
7. K. Dhara, Y. Hori, R. Baba and K. Kikuchi, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 11534.
8. Y. Ren and T. Baumgartner, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 2669.
9. C. Shi, Z. Guo, Y. Yan, S. Zhu, Y. Xie, Y. S. Zhao, W. Zhu and H. Tian, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2013, **5**, 192.
10. J. Luo, Z. Xie, J. W. Y. Lam, L. Cheng, H. Chen, C. Qiu, H. S. Kwok, X. Zhan, Y. Liu, D. Zhu and B. Z. Tang, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 1740.
11. X. Huang, X. Gu, G. Zhang and D. Zhang, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 12195.
12. S. Li, S. M. Langenegger and R. Haner, *Chem. Commun.*, 2013, **49**, 5835.
13. W. Wu, S. Ye, R. Tang, L. Huang, Q. Li, G. Yu, Y. Liu, J. Qin and Z. Li, *Polymer*, 2012, **53**, 3163.
14. B. K. An, S. K. Kwon, S. D. Jung and S. Y. Park, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 14410.
15. S. J. Li, B. K. An, S. D. Jung, M. A. Chung and S. Y. Park, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2004, **43**, 6346.
16. M. Rosoff, Ed. *Vesicles*, Dekker, New York, 1996.
17. A. M. Carmona-Ribeiro, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1992, **21**, 209.
18. S. Dutta Choudhury, A. C. Bhasikuttan, H. Pal and J. Mohanty, *Langmuir*, 2011, **27**, 12312.
19. R. Bhowmick, R. Alam, T. Mistri, D. Bhattacharya, P. Karmakar and M. Ali, *Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2015, **7**, 7476.
20. R. Bhowmick, A. S. M. Islam, A. Katarkar, K. Chaudhuri and M. Ali, *Analyst*, 2016, **141**, 225.
21. H. N. Kim, W. X. Ren, J. S. Kim and J. Yoon, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **4**, 3210.
22. D. G. He, X. X. He, K. M. Wang, Y. X. Zhao and Z. Zou, *Langmuir*, 2013, **29**, 5896.
23. Y. C. Shih, C. Y. Ke, C. J. Yu, C. Y. Lu and W. L. Tseng, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2014, **6**, 17437.
24. P. B. Tchounwou, W. K. Ayensu, N. Ninashvili and D. Sutton, *Environ. Toxicol.*, 2003, **18**, 149.
25. A. C. Bittner (Jr.), D. Echeverria, J. S. Woods, H. Vasken. Aposhian, C. Naleway, M. D. Martin, R. K. Mahurin, N. J. Heyer and M. Cianciola,

- Neurotoxicol. Teratol.*, 1998, **20**, 429.
26. Mercury Study Report to Congress, United States Environmental Protection Agency, Volume V : Health Effects of Mercury and Mercury Compounds, EPA-452/R-97-007 December 1997.
 27. M. Suresh, A. Ghosh and A. Das, *Chem. Commun.*, 2008, 3906.
 28. O. A. Bozdemir, R. Guliyev, O. Buyukcakir, S. Selcuk, S. Kolemen, G. Gulseren, T. Nalbantoglu, H. Boyaci and E. U. Akkaya, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 8029.
 29. A. Thakur, S. Sardar and S. Ghosh, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **50**, 7066.
 30. J. R. Lakowicz, "Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy", 3rd. ed., Springer, New York, 2006, **67**.
 31. R. P. Haugland, "The Handbook : A Guide to Fluorescent Probes and Labeling Technologies", 10th ed., Invitrogen Corp., Karlsbad, CA, 2005.
 32. H. Y. Lee, K. M. K. Swamy, J. Y. Jung, G. Kim and J. Yoon, *Sens. Actuators (B)*, 2013, **182**, 530.
 33. X. Chen, T. Pradhan, F. Wang, J. S. Kim and J. Yoon, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 1910.
 34. K. Bera, A. K. Das, M. Nag and S. Basak, *Anal. Chem.*, 2014, **86**, 2740.
 35. V. Dujols, F. Ford and A. W. Czarnik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 7386.
 36. J. S. Wu, I. C. Hwang, K. S. Kim and J. S. Kim, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 907.
 37. R. Alam, T. Mistri, P. Mondal, D. Das, S. K. Mandal, A. R. Khuda-Bukhsh and M. Ali, *Dalton Trans.*, 2014, **43**, 2566.
 38. R. Alam, T. Mistri, A. Katarkar, K. Chaudhuri, S. K. Mandal, A. R. Khuda-Bukhsh, K. K. Das and M. Ali, *Analyst*, 2014, **139**, 4022.
 39. R. Bhowmick, M. Dolai, R. Alam, T. Mistri, A. Katarkar, K. Chaudhuri and M. Ali, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 41784.